

WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES: A RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the period of formation of women's rights and equality with men. It also comparatively examines the initial recruitment of women into the law enforcement system. The current role of female employees in the system of internal affairs bodies (police) has been investigated.

Keywords: women's rights, law enforcement agencies, police, development, combating crime.

Women's rights are not just a historical and legal phenomenon; they are connected with politics, spirituality and enlightenment, religious beliefs and philosophy, and social changes in society. Women's rights are multifaceted and complex, manifesting differently in various eras. Looking at the evolution of historical and legal sources, the emergence of norms on women's rights is linked to the appearance of the first legal norms on human rights. For example, according to unwritten (oral) rules of antiquity, customs that prohibit involving women in hard labor and stipulate that women should engage in housekeeping and child-rearing while men go hunting[1] are the first manifestations of norms relating to women's rights. They developed in harmony with the evolution of general legal norms, improved through different historical periods, and reached the level of modern standards.

With the development of industrial society in the late 18th - early 19th centuries in Western European countries, and then in the mid-19th century in the USA, women began to be more actively involved in various spheres of labor and production processes. In 1830, a new term "emancipated woman" (liberated) appeared in France, and in 1867 the first international women's society was established in London[2].

The main directions of the women's movement in these periods included the struggle for suffrage, access to higher education, the right to a profession, and economic equality (participation in social production and financial independence). During this period, the greatest achievements were observed mainly in the USA. The struggle of women for their rights coincided with the abolition of slavery (1865).

Women's entry into the law enforcement sphere was reflected in the following well-known events:

- In 1845, for the first time in New York, two women were officially hired as guards in women's prisons;
- In 1893, in Chicago, Maria Owens was appointed a police officer for a monthly salary (her husband was a police officer, and if he died, she was hired to provide financial compensation to the deceased's spouse for the loss of a breadwinner);

- In 1908, on the eve of the World's Fair in Portland, a special department was created to improve security and public morality (reducing the level of prostitution), headed by a woman named Laura Baldwin. Although he held the position of police officer, his rights were limited.

Since the beginning of the 20th century, the involvement of female police officers in law enforcement in European countries and the USA has been associated with the need to work with women and children who have committed crimes. The increase in the number of women in the police force in European countries was associated with the demographic problems that arose during and after the Second World War, as well as the increase in crime rates among women and minors during this period.

During the second wave of the feminist movement in North America and European countries in the 1960s and 1980s, legal documents were adopted protecting women's rights to professional education in the police sphere, ensuring their full participation in law enforcement activities.

In 1964, the US passed the Civil Rights Act, which established the end of discrimination against women in all spheres of public life.

In the 1970s-1980s, although an increase in crime and an increase in the number of police officers was observed in the USA, it did not yield the expected high results in the fight against crime. Also during this period, several legislative acts were adopted in the USA, which positively influenced the increase in the number of women in the justice and law enforcement system: the Law on Safe Streets (1968) and the Law on Combating Crime (1973) [3].

According to the law on combating crime, it was established that education in state educational institutions and police academies is not prevented regardless of race, gender[3].

Taking into account the peculiarities of the decentralized law enforcement system in the USA, it was divided into three components: federal, state-level, and local administration (administrative district, settlement). The majority of employees, about 60 percent, worked at the lower level. In the 1980s and 1990s, it was in the USA that the new concept of "community policing" emerged, since working according to the old model of combating crime in the new conditions was ineffective. According to it, the police assigned to the area are aimed at solving the problems of the population living in that area, and the main principle is also aimed at solving the problems of the population. Organized the prevention and prophylaxis of offenses[4].

To establish close contact with the population in solving various problems, it was necessary, firstly, to have high communicative abilities, to obtain the necessary information, to resolve conflict situations "peacefully"; secondly, to quickly establish contact with children, women, the elderly, people with disabilities, mentally ill people, especially through the ability to establish reliable communication with different gender and age categories. Since these characteristics are more developed in women, their verbal intelligence (ability) is higher, the demand for female police officers in this new category of "communal police" has increased.

Thus, even now in the USA, female police officers are working, especially in the "communal police," in forensic services, in the investigation of crimes, in working with juvenile offenders, and also in the field of forensic medicine. According to analytical data, female police officers, compared to men, try to resolve dangerous situations without resorting to violent methods and firearms, which serves to enhance the authority of the police in society. Perhaps that's why more female police officers work in large police departments.

According to statistics, women in the US police force in 1980

If this indicator was 5 percent, then by 2014 it reached 12 percent. However, the distribution of the number of women in different departments and areas of work differs. For example, in 2017-2018, the proportion of female police officers in major US cities was: in New York - 18%, in Los Angeles - 18%, in Chicago - 24%.

Also, female employees in law enforcement structures at the federal level are represented as follows: in the US Capitol Police - 19%; Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) - 19%; Federal Bureau of Prisons - 14%; In the Department for Combating Narcotics - 10%. The proportion of female employees is also present in other services, such as Federal Marshals, Immigration and Customs Police, Forest Service, Postal Control Service, Chief Inspector's Office, and Secret Service. It should also be noted that in the management structures of US law enforcement agencies - 7% are women[5].

Since the time of the Great Revolution (1789-1799), law enforcement agencies in France consist of the national police (civil servants) and the national gendarmerie (military personnel). Currently, 70% of crimes are solved by the police, and 80% of suspects are apprehended.

In 1977, several female officers were appointed to the positions of police commissioners, and between 1972 and 1999, the number of women in the police remained stable at 14.5%. Although in 2015 it was 19 percent, and since 2017 it has been stable, i.e., 27 percent, their distribution by directions is uneven. For example, in the National Police Research Institute - 61%; in the National Police Personnel Department - 41%; in the department - 43%; in the area of international cooperation - 19%.

The main tasks of the French National Gendarmerie include ensuring public safety and judicial activity. There are fewer women than in the police force, and until 1982, female employees performed only administrative duties (personnel management).

From 1987, women were eligible to receive the rank of gendarmerie officer, and in 2013, Isabel G. de Meritens was appointed for the first time to the post of general director of the gendarmerie.

By decree of March 3, 1992, differences in the admission of men and women to the police service were abolished, except for special units - republican security detachments. Currently, both in the police and gendarmerie, women take the same tests as men, with only differences in physical load standards. A woman in the gendarmerie can apply for a leadership position after 10 years of experience[6].

The first woman in the UK police force was Edith Smith (1915), who was authorized to investigate crimes involving women and arrest perpetrators. With the adoption of the Equal Monthly Payment Act (1970) and the Sexual Discrimination Act (1975), women in police units had the same ranks, responsibilities, and rights as men. In 2007, the proportion of female police officers was 23%, while in 2017 it remained stable at 30%. Female constables (the lowest police officer) receive additional training from psychologists throughout their careers and mainly work with children, adolescents, and women who are victims of domestic and sexual violence in "family protection" police departments.

In Great Britain, the first International Police Women's Association was established (1950), whose main task was "strengthening, enhancing, and uniting the authority of women working in the field of justice at the international level." In 1989, the "European Police Women Network" was established in the Netherlands, based on which conferences and

seminars were held, information and experience were exchanged, which contributed to the popularization of the activities of female police officers in the police services of the European Union[7]. By 2014, the number of member countries was 28. Sexual harassment, on an equal basis with men, encompassed the most pressing issues, such as "the same salary for the same work," career and rank advancement without any prohibitions, and "guarantees and social package." We know that there are no uniform standards in the activities of police officers. In the USA, Germany, and Great Britain, female police officers have equal rights with men in performing functional duties, and they have the opportunity to file a complaint if their rights are infringed upon or if there is pressure to promote them (even if there are vacancies, only men are hired). The only difference between male police officers and female police officers lies in the established standards of physical activity.

In the 20th - early 21st centuries, in most countries of the world, women began to work as state police officers or freely hired employees. The involvement of women in the police was associated with enhancing the authority of law enforcement agencies and bringing the police and civil society institutions closer together. In general, it served to increase the effectiveness of measures taken by the police to ensure public safety, increase confidence in state power and its activity in ensuring the safety of the population, as well as stabilize the internal environment in society [8].

Currently, women police officers serve in law enforcement agencies in Eastern Asian countries, Latin America, and Africa, as well as in European countries. For example, in Israel, women actively serve in both the military and civilian police. In Iran, however, the admission of women to law enforcement is limited, and female police officers mainly monitor women's compliance with the "code of clothing for women in Islam." In India, female police officers do not patrol the streets, but perform all duties related to child and female delinquency.

In the states of the USSR, the first female militiamen began to work in 1919, and their activities not only positively affected the sphere, but also led to an increase in the number of women working in the internal affairs system. During the Second World War, the recruitment of women into the police service increased due to the departure of men to the front (police officers). It was during the war that letters of gratitude were issued to female police officers for their initiative in service and successful completion of tasks. For example, in 1943, certificates of appreciation were awarded to 28 female police officers serving in the Chuvash Republic[9].

In Russia, the International Women's Congress of Women Police Officers was held for the first time in St. Petersburg on March 21-24, 1995, addressing the problems in this area and "Police. Woman. Humanism" was dedicated to the conceptual directions. In Russia, 146 thousand people served in the internal affairs bodies in 1997, of which about 15% were women. In some areas, the proportion of women prevailed, for example, 71% - passport and visa services; 61% - correctional inspection work; 58% - Inspection for Minors; Among the psychologists in the Ministry of Internal Affairs, women constituted 53%. Also, in 1997, in units traditionally considered "men's" service, namely, in the operational-search department - 2800 people; in criminal investigation departments - 1000 people; in the service of district inspectors - 562 people; 4) in units for combating organized crime groups - 670 units; 5) in special services - 219 women.

Women have been working in the internal affairs bodies (police) of Uzbekistan since the creation of the system, and in the 1950s, women were also accepted into the police service.

However, their number and role have increased significantly as a result of recent reforms. The state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with bringing great innovations to the life of society, also required new approaches to the attitude towards the individual, his rights and freedoms. First of all, unlike the previous system, the state required a change in its attitude towards people, including women. Uzbekistan's independence marked the beginning of a new era in protecting women's rights alongside human rights. Women's access to education and work in various fields has been strengthened. Due to the need to increase the level of security of the population and close interaction with society, the active involvement of women in the sphere has begun. In the 2000s, programs were developed to promote gender equality and empower women in law enforcement agencies.

Today, the proportion of female employees in the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with other spheres, is increasing, with women constituting about 9% of the personnel of internal affairs bodies[10].

As in the developed countries analyzed above, the rights and obligations of women serving in the internal affairs bodies of our Republic are the same as men, differing only in physical loads, and separate standards have not been established. Nevertheless, female employees of the internal affairs bodies work in the departments of offenses, combating crime, operational-search, investigation, criminology, women's affairs, road safety, patrol posts, migration, and other departments.

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